

A Case Report of Penetrating Head Injury to a Non-Trauma Centre

Babajide Adenekan

Specialist Registrar, Emergency Medicine, Department of Emergency Medicine, North Manchester General Hospital, Manchester, United Kingdom

Osayamen Iyekekpolor

Medical student, Emergency Medicine, Department of Emergency Medicine, North Manchester General Hospital, Manchester, United Kingdom

More Information

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Abstract

Penetrating head injuries have high morbidity and mortality rates with resultant debilitating neurological deficit for survivors. Most of these patients present to Level A trauma centres with comprehensive tertiary care facilities, however some of these patients could present as “walk-ins” to a regional non-trauma centre. This could be the case in a regional, district, urban hospital like ours. Deliberate acts of violence among youths could result in penetrating head injury with a machete. Early clinical and neuro-radiological assessment to identify and prevent life-threatening complications is vital.

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Introduction

Penetrating head injury encompasses all traumatic injury that breaches the skull. Although they are uncommon, when inflicted, they often have a poor prognosis [1].

These injuries commonly result from violent, intentional attempts to seriously injure or even kill another person and in unfortunate circumstances can result in debilitating injury [2]. These injuries could be a potentially life threatening condition if not managed appropriately in the emergency room [3].

A machete is a multipurpose tool typically used in agricultural or possibly household contexts. When used with violent intent, it can be used as a close-range weapon [4]. Injuries sustained from machete wounds should be treated as a neurosurgical emergency, especially if associated with neurological deficit [5]. Immediate and aggressive management of a machete head injury involves prompt clinical assessment, intravenous antibiotics, tetanus prophylaxis and early operative intervention - if needed it will reduce the risk of complications and improve prognosis [6].

Increasing urban violence and use of blunt and sharp objects could lead to increased presentation of these injuries; nevertheless, they are associated with good

outcomes if immediately attended to at presentation [7]. There is a male predominance of machete head injury presentation. A study in South-Eastern Nigeria revealed a male to female ratio of 10:1 [4]. There is limited literature on the reports of violent machete head injury in urban teaching hospitals in Manchester.

Case Report

We report a case of a 21-year-old male who presented to our emergency department with penetrating machete injury to the head.

The patient had self-presented to the emergency department, stating he had been assaulted in the community. Immediate review revealed several machete injuries to different parts of the body, including his head, arms and legs. The most significant injury was the penetrating head injury with a resultant large haemorrhage from his scalp vessels.

Our patient remained conscious throughout with a Glasgow Coma Score (GCS) of 15. A primary survey revealed a large scalp wound to the central fronto-parietal region with boggy haematoma. Injuries to other parts of the body were cleaned and simple sutures applied.

Clinical examination and computed tomography scanning of the head revealed open scalp laceration

and penetrating injury to the scalp (see Figures 1-3 respectively).

Figure 1: Clinical Pictures of Scalp Laceration at Presentation to Emergency Department

Figure 2: Computed Tomography Image of Scalp Laceration with Hematoma

Treatment initiated at presentation was intravenous analgesia, thorough wound cleaning, blood replacement and intravenous antibiotics with tetanus prophylaxis. Initial suturing of the scalp wound was done to control haemorrhage. He also received blood product replacement due to the serious haemorrhage from the scalp wound. He was transferred to the neurosurgical centre for further management of his head injury. Follow up revealed the patients had a re-

washout of the scalp wound and a secondary closure of the scalp laceration with intravenous antibiotics administration.

Figure 3: Computed Tomography (Bone Window) of the Skull Bones

Discussion

Machete injuries are an uncommon presentation to urban district general hospitals like ours; although not part of the trauma regional network that receives pre-alerted trauma patients, we do attend to walk-in trauma patients with penetrating injuries similar to that of our presented case.

Penetrating head injuries have high morbidity and mortality. Most of these occur in urban centres due to interpersonal violence among youths with intent of grievous bodily harm. Penetrating head injuries can cause complex neurosurgical emergencies hence urgency of intervention at presentation is high to prevent subsequent infection and further deterioration of neurological status. Evidence from Nicaragua revealed that an aggressive approach in the management of penetrating head injuries due to a machete results in good outcomes with a far reduced disability upon hospital discharge [8].

An algorithm published in the Journal World Neurosurgery by De Holanda et al., showed the critical steps to be taken in the management of penetrating cranial injuries from presentation. This has been adopted globally and with good success reported in the literature. The prognosis for these patients also depends on their GCS at presentation. Our patient had

GCS of 15/15 throughout their emergency department stay before transfer. The algorithm (see Figure 4) highlights the early importance of neuro-radiological assessment and further intervention in the presence of transdural penetration of the missile. Our patient did not have the missile still present at presentation hence no need for urgent craniotomy for removal of same.

Figure 4. Algorithm of Neurosurgical Management of Nonmissile Penetrating Cranial Lesions. AED, Antiepileptic Drug; NMP, Nonmissile Penetrating
Source: [9]

We did however institute rapid antibiotic administration, haemorrhage control (with blood product administration) and tetanus prophylaxis. We did not institute anti-epileptic prophylaxis as there was no breach of the dura.

Conclusion

Penetrating head injuries can present as ‘walk-ins’ in non-neurosurgical and trauma centres like ours. Immediate recognition of such injuries in these patients helps alert the emergency physician of the potential complications of delayed treatment. Early clinical and neuroradiological assessment alongside haemorrhage control, blood product replacement and tetanus prophylaxis with anti-seizure prophylaxis (in cases of dura breach) should be of priority in the early stages of management of these patients. In addition, early liaison

with the neurosurgical specialists is vital in the management of these patients especially those who present with reduced GCS.

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Ethical Statement

The authors have identified no ethical concerns in undertaking this article.

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest highlighted by the authors.

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